

EU POLYRISK

Towards a Risk Assessment Framework for Micro- and Nanoplastic

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The general risk assessment paradigm

Substance Identity

Chemical Composition (Impurities?)

In some cases incl. key characteristics (e.g. for nanomaterials: size, morphology, surface area, surface treatment)

Exposure Assessment

Who? Route? How often? How long? Dose? etc.

Hazard Identification

What health problems/ adverse effects? Target organ(s)?

Dose Response Assessment

Threshold? How does hazard change with dose?

Risk characterization

Is there a risk? For whom? How big is the risk?

Risk assessment for Micro- and Nanoplastics (MNPs)

Useful Concepts: Grouping

"Substances whose **physicochemical, toxicological and ecotoxicological properties** are likely to be **similar** or follow a regular pattern **as a result of structural similarity** may be considered as a group" (REACH, Annex XI, 1.5).

Analogue approach small number of structurally similar substances (usually no trends visible)
(a given **toxicological property** of one substance (**source**) can be **used to predict the same property** for another substance (**target**))

Category approach several substances of structural similarity substances (trends may be visible)
(**endpoint specific**)

Grouping approaches for nanomaterials

Stone et al. Nano Today 2020 35, 100941
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nantod.2020.100941>

Useful Concepts: IATAs

Integrated Approaches to Testing and Assessment

OECD IATA Activities

<https://www.oecd.org/chemicalsafety/risk-assessment/iata/>

- flexible approaches for chemical safety assessment
- integrate data from multiple methods/ sources, may include New Approach Methods (NAMs) such as high throughput screening or computational methods
- **provide a logical combinations of tests and assessments** (outcome of one step determines the next); **overall assessment conducted with a minimum of new experiments**
- can be based on **AOP concepts**

Useful Concepts: AOPs

Adverse Outcome Pathways

AOP: Conceptual construct that portrays existing knowledge concerning the linkages between a direct **molecular initiating event** and an **adverse outcome** via several **key events**

(Ankley *et al.*, Environ Toxicol Chem 2010)

Pulmonary injury leading to fibrosis

Clippinger *et al.*, Arch Toxicol (2016).

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Fibre Toxicity

The Fibre Toxicity Paradigm is well established for inorganic fibres (in particular asbestos).
Classical Fibre Toxicity Paradigm: Respirable, long and biopersistent fibres are carcinogenic.
WHO Criteria: Length > 5 μm , Diameter < 3 μm , Aspect Ratio >3, Biopersistence

Donaldson et al 2010 PFT 2010, 7:5

Nanofibres challenge the classical fibre toxicity paradigm:

Rigidity hypothesis: Long, rigid fibres withstand bending during phagocytosis but flexible, thin fibres curl up.

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Poorly Soluble, Low Tox (PSLT) Particles

Characteristics:

- **Respirable particles** (MMAD < 10 μm), aspect ratio <3
- **Biopersistence** (pulmonary retention half-time of 60–80 d)
 - Solubility testing** (“release of compounds”)
 - Persistence of particles** (incl. clearance by alv. macrophages)
- **Low Toxicity**
 - associated to **Inflammatory Potential & Reactivity**

Lung Overload

Lung particle overload: old school –new insights?
Borm, Cassee, Oberdörster Particle and Fibre Toxicology 12
<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12989-015-0086-4>

OECD Polymer of Low Concern (PLC)

OECD expert group classified polymers to simplify risk assessment (OECD, 2009):

Polymers of Low Concern (PLC) and **Polymers of Potential Concern**

PLC are deemed to have insignificant environmental and human health impacts.

➤ **Number-average molecular weight (M_n) ≥ 1000 Da**

➤ **Low molecular weight, oligomeric species (i.e., < 1000 Da and/or < 500 Da species)**

The higher the oligomer content, the more likely a polymer was to display concern. Most potential health concern polymers had $M_n < 10000$ Da and oligomer content values of $> 1\%$.

➤ **Reactive functional groups**

Functional groups that are known to be associated with toxicity of polymers

➤ **Water solubility**

Polymers with water solubilities < 10 mg/L showed generally low health concern

In addition, other useful criteria were discussed (e.g. **polymer's stability** or **residual monomer content**).

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POLYRISK Real World Scenarios

Air exposure at tire rubber refurbishing workplaces

Utrecht University

Urban and rural outdoor air ambient MNP

Textile fibre workplace exposure

MNP in bottled drinking water

Norwegian Institute of Public Health

Indoor Soccer Players exposure to rubber granulate-MNP

POLYRISK Method Development for Sampling & Characterization

Example: Correlative microscopy (for Identification and Counting of MNP-Aerosols on Nucleopore filters)

POLYRISK Hazard Characterization

KEY EVENTS CENTRAL TO MANY INFLAMMATORY DISEASE OUTCOMES

Inflammation

- 1) Cell Activation
(**macrophages**, epithelial cells, neutrophils, myeloid cells)
- 2) Inflammatory mediators release
- 3) Recruitment of e.g. neutrophils

Representing the Process of Inflammation as Key Events in Adverse Outcome Pathways

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Reactivity & Cellular ox. stress

- 1) Acellular particle reactivity (e.g. FRAS, DCFDA assay)
- 2) Cellular oxidative stress (in vitro)
(various assays, **macrophages**, epithelial cells, neutrophils, myeloid cells)

Thank you for your attention.

